

Organization of Medical and Pedagogical Control of Athletes

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Abstract:

A field that studies the effects of physical exercise and sports on the human body, some of its systems and organs. The main task is to study the effect of physical exercise on the body as a factor that strengthens health, increases working capacity and prolongs life, and to develop rational methods of physical exercise and sports training.

Keywords: pedagogical control, medical control, biological supply, operative inspection, training.

INTRODUCTION.

At the current stage of society's development, issues of training athletes are of particular importance. Many studies of our country and foreign experts are devoted to the problems of physical fitness. Most of them are mainly aimed at training physical qualities (strength, speed, endurance, etc.) in adult athletes. This manual helps to reveal the problems of developing physical abilities in athletes. The methodological manual consists of 6 sections, and the introduction contains information about the tasks and components of the science of sports medicine. In the first part, the purpose and tasks of sports medicine. Sports selection and sports orientation. Medical care of competitions, which covers the history of sports medicine, 5 periods and 2 parts. The second section consists of medical control methods used in sports medicine. In the third section, physical development, methods of its examination and assessment, i.e., anthropometric indicators, are covered in detail. The fourth section describes the functional status of all systems in athletes during normal and pathological periods. In the fifth section, sports pathology, means of restoring sports performance are highlighted. The sixth section contains information on the list of used literature.

MAIN PART.

Medical-pedagogical supervision is defined as examinations conducted by a doctor and a coach during training, physical education classes or during competitions. With the help of such control,

the effect of physical exercises on the body of those engaged in physical education and sports is evaluated, the level of functional physical fitness of the body is determined, and the training process is improved based on these checks. In the medical-pedagogical control, operative (in a short period of time), daily and every-stage inspections are carried out, which are included in the structure of the medical biological support of the training of athletes.

Short-term training effect is evaluated in operative tests. The following forms of medical-pedagogical control are used in the process of operative examinations:

- a) inspections conducted during the entire training, in each part of the training;
- b) inspections conducted before training and 20-30 minutes after training;
- c) morning and evening on the training day.

Checks after each part of the training during the training are carried out only if the trainer is interested in the correct structure of the training. If medical-pedagogical control is organized in such a form, certain indicators are checked before training, after each part of training, after performing an exercise, after rest and after training. It should be said that medical-pedagogical control during the entire training is labor-intensive and interferes with the training process to some extent. Therefore, this form of medical-pedagogical control is used in cases where it is very necessary. It is possible to evaluate the amount of load and the level of preparation of the athlete by comparing the performance indicators of the participants before and after the training. In order to study the effect of the load on the body from one day's training, tests are carried out in the morning and in the evening.

The effect of training after a certain period of time, that is, in the last phases of recovery, is evaluated in daily tests. The form of organization of such checks may be as follows:

- a) every morning before training;
- b) morning and evening for several days;
- c) at the beginning and at the end of one or two microcycles;
- g) one day after training, sometimes 1-2 days later.

In order to plan loads into the microcycle, determine the day of high-intensity training, and determine the level of recovery after various types of training, checks are carried out daily throughout the microcycle.

Inspections at each stage are of great importance for planning and personalizing the training process, as it evaluates the cumulative effect of training at a given stage. In this case, it is determined to what extent the task assigned to this stage has been completed.

By comparing the work done, the training methods and tools used, with the changes that have occurred throughout the entire stage, it is necessary to draw the necessary conclusions for planning the next training process. The doctor's task in performing these tasks is to evaluate the general working ability of the organism, changes in its functional state. Psychological readiness should be assessed. The task of the coach is to evaluate the level of functional training of the athlete.

Inspections at each stage should be carried out once every 2-3 months. Checks should be carried out after a day of rest, 1-2 hours after breakfast. Before the tests, the athlete should not do physical exercise.

The coach and the doctor, the athlete, by analyzing the indicators of self-examination, can get the information that is important for them. These data, combined with daily checks, various tests, help to evaluate the effectiveness of the training microcycle structure. Every athlete should keep a self-monitoring diary.

The diary should also contain information about mood, sleep, appetite, work ability. In the diary, there should also be indicators of pulse and respiratory rate in 1 minute, vital capacity of the lungs, weight, arterial blood pressure and arm dynamometry. You can also write the following in the diary: deterioration of health, violation of work order, etc.

In conclusion, it can be said that in the organization of medical-pedagogical supervision of athletes, the doctor, coach and athlete should work together.

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